

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF BUSINESS ACTIVITY

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Abstract: The article examines the role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the economy, as well as stimulating the development of entrepreneurial activity in Uzbekistan. Scientifically based proposals and recommendations have been developed.

Key words: business, entrepreneurship, small business entity, micro-firms, shares, intellectual resources, innovation process, gross national product, firms, currency exchange, shareholding.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning iqtisodiyotdagi o'рни, shuningdek, O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishni rag'batlantirish ko'rib chiqiladi. Ilmiy asoslangan taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: biznes, tadbirkorlik, kichik biznes sub'ekti, mikrofirmalar, aksiyalar, intellektual resurslar, innovatsion jarayon, yalpi milliy mahsulot, firmalar, valyuta birjasi, aksiyalar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства в экономике, а также стимулирование развития предпринимательской деятельности в Узбекистане. Разработаны научно обоснованные предложения и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: бизнес, предпринимательство, субъект малого предпринимательства, микрофирмы, акции, интеллектуальные ресурсы, инновационный процесс, валовой национальный продукт, фирмы, обмен валюты, пакет акций.

The business sector is one of the leading sectors, which mainly determines the rate of economic growth, the state of employment of the population, the composition and quality of the gross domestic product. Small business development responds to global trends aimed at forming a flexible mixed economy, a complex synthesis of the competitive market mechanism, and a combination of ownership forms, including state regulation of large, medium and small-scale products, and the formation of an appropriate economic model. Small business is the basis of market economy.

Small business objectively exists as a relatively independent department of the modern market economy, characterized by the presence and interdependence of enterprises of various sizes and sizes, including small enterprises. While big business provides the basic needs of the country's economy, small businesses take their place in the market, satisfy local demand or special needs in the area of innovation, including products and services.

In the social economy, entrepreneurship is a decisive factor in creating an economic basis for solving important problems of social development.

Entrepreneurship creates conditions for expanding the population's employment and increasing their income, creates a special social environment, mitigates the sharp angles of possible conflicts between the segments of society, develops competition, and at the same time has the benefit of consumers and society. has a significant impact on the formation of competitive prices for goods. In general, it serves to expand the services provided in the areas of health and education.

Within the scope of the topic, let's dwell in detail on the definitions given to the improvement of the innovative activity of the main studied economic category of small business entities.

In particular, R. Cantilon evaluates entrepreneurship as a risk-taker, who buys goods whose profit is not limited and whose price is certain, but whose selling price is uncertain. Schumpeter identified five important aspects of entrepreneurship: production of new goods unknown to consumers; application of new production and commercialization of existing goods; acquisition of new goods; use of new raw materials; shows the improvement of the network.

An entrepreneur is a person who implements new combinations - he says. SGʻulomov said that small business and entrepreneurship in any conditions, even in economic depression, in the period of inflation, even when the percentage of loans is extremely high, even in cases where the future is unknown without the necessary infrastructure, the higher the risk. he lives in spite of it. According to AOʻlmasov, "Small business is the material and financial resources (capital) of people (property) entities intended for economic turnover, earning income", while Yo. Abdullaev refers to entrepreneurship - in accordance with legal documents, aimed at obtaining income (profit), legal entities and individuals.

He defined the problem of small business as an entrepreneurial activity carried out under his own property responsibility by taking risks through the production of products.

In order to increase the efficiency of the work carried out in this regard in our country, paragraph 4 of the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 14, 2018 "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of the commercialization of the results of improving the results of scientific and scientific and technical activities" The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with the Ministry of Innovative Development, will implement innovative ideas and advanced technologies within the funds allocated under the "Science" article in forming the parameters of the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019 and beyond. at least 20 percent of the funds will be directed to increase ^[2]. Decree No. PF-150 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 9, 2022 "On additional measures to further improve the activities of the State Fund for the Support of Entrepreneurial Activities" was received. Also, in the process of research, the process of formation of innovative development directions of entrepreneurial activity was studied using logical thinking, scientific observation, systematic approach methods. Using the methods of induction and deduction, statistical and comparative analysis, the conditions and possibilities of innovative development of entrepreneurship are substantiated.

It is very important to create innovative innovations and their practical application in increasing the efficiency of business activities. It is also known from international experience that the level of development of the economy and society largely depends on innovative activities. There are several reasons to prioritize the rapid development of entrepreneurship based on the ongoing reforms and the experience of developed countries, where the importance of the sector in filling the domestic market with necessary goods and services is of great importance.

Indeed, small business entities are filling the domestic market with local goods and services, supplying large enterprises with components and parts, and increasing the country's export potential. This can be seen from the fact that the country is increasing its position in the export potential. The role of small business in foreign economic activity is gradually expanding. Its share in the export volume will be 22.3 percent in 2021, which is an increase of 8.6 percent compared to 2010 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The share of small business in the country's exports in 2010-2021, %

Export plays an important role in the foreign economic activity of any country. The development of our country's economy is directly dependent on the growth of export potential. During the years of independence, the export potential of our country changed radically. In this, the role of small business is incomparable. Today, business entities not only fill the domestic consumer market with import-substituting goods, but also offer high-quality, competitive goods to the world market. Small business is becoming the most important sector in the country's economy.

Also, increasing the contribution of small business to the country's economy, creating small industrial zones, improving the investment environment and competitive environment, expanding the volume of public procurement within the framework of public-private partnership with small business, and strengthening mutually beneficial cooperation between large and small enterprises. , we can see by involving business entities in innovation processes.

We should also emphasize that financial support for successful and promising small enterprises that have sufficient export potential, but at the same time do not have enough capital for further development, requires great importance. These measures help to create more jobs in the field of effective small business, increase access to the world market, increase the country's export potential and increase the income of the population.

Today, the development of the private sector, the expansion of business activities and the provision of legal guarantees serve as the basis for the development of market sectors under conditions of free competition and the production of competitive products. In the economies of developed countries, the main part of gross production falls on the private sector.

As a result of the legal support of entrepreneurship and small business entities in our country and the reduction of tax rates set for them, this industry has become the leading link of the economy today. The development of small business and private entrepreneurship entities in our country, their share in the country's gross national product is growing more and more ^[3].

The current stage of the development of the world economy requires ensuring the continuity of innovative processes and increasing their scope. In such conditions, the efficiency of small business and private entrepreneurship depends on the development of their activities based on scientific and technological achievements, the introduction of large-scale production of products with high scientific capacity in the industry, as well as the commercialization of the results of scientific and scientific and technical activities. , is determined by its orientation to practice.

The advantage of innovative entrepreneurship requires adequate organizational mechanisms to search for innovative ideas, to implement new projects, and to process them. The strength of the organizational forms of innovative entrepreneurship is determined by the traditional methods of capital production. The strength of the organizational structure of innovative entrepreneurship shows the development of specific tasks of the innovative process, the provision of resources, the possession of a clear information base, and the scope of the implementation of the innovative project. It is at this time that the organizational system of innovative entrepreneurship is related to the general characteristics and the absorption of the risk factor in them, the uncertainty in the achievement of the goal and the final results.

The advantages of innovative business activity in business entities are as follows:

- high interest in innovation;
- conducting scientific research in a narrow scope (in a specific direction);
- high ability to effectively direct intellectual resources to the production of the final product;
- availability of high "risk" work that cannot be carried out by large enterprises with low cost and efficiency.

The organizational and legal foundations of innovative entrepreneurship are different. In times of developed market economy, there are special venture firms that work with great risk and conduct research on creating new goods and services.

The founders of venture firms, engineers and scientists, hand over the results of their research to experimental, patent and cooperative firms.

Another regional organizational type of innovative entrepreneurship is scientific technological parks (tech-parks). This organizational system helps to organize the production and sale of innovative business products on the market, thereby helping to develop innovative activities in small businesses.

The search for new ideas and their implementation is the most important and at the same time the most difficult task of entrepreneurship. Because, in this case, an entrepreneur is required not only to think creatively and find new solutions, but also to have perspective thinking and the ability to see the future. A special tool of innovative entrepreneurship is the innovative form of entrepreneurial thinking ^[8].

It should be noted that any innovative activity is entrepreneurship, because it is the search for new ideas, the search for necessary resources; creating and managing an enterprise; is based on obtaining material income and personal satisfaction from its result.

However, not every business can be innovative, only those that enable the use of business income and the diffusion of innovative products as a result of their creation can be called innovative. Organizations carrying out innovative activities are innovative business entities.

Investing in innovative entrepreneurship by the state has its own advantages in conducting a rational investment policy. The stock market is the most important economic instrument for attracting free funds of competent investors. The liquidity of shares, advertising and information activities of the company, the analysis of the movement of shares put up for sale on the currency exchange platform and the sale of a package of shares to foreign investors serve to further improve the state of the stock market ^[9].

The decree of the President of the Republic “On the strategy for the development of New Uzbekistan in 2022-2026” defined the strategy for the development of the country’s economy in 2022 and beyond. The chapter of the development strategy entitled “Rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates” defines the tasks of rapid development of entrepreneurship and increasing its contribution to the national economy. One of these priorities is the creation of a favorable business environment for the wide development of small business and private entrepreneurship, strict prevention of illegal interference by the state, law enforcement and control agencies in the activities of business structures, further development of private property and private entrepreneurship, This is evidenced by the fact that it is a matter of giving complete freedom to the industry, removing all the obstacles and restrictions that stand in the way. The rapid development of the economy of our country, the improvement of the standard of living and the quality of life of the population are in many ways closely related to the perspective of small business.

As a result of the implementation of the decisions taken on the support of entrepreneurship, the reduction of inspection work, the reduction of financial and time costs for doing business, as a result of the introduction of the registration notification system, there are positive trends in their foreign trade activity indicators. . State support of small business entities producing import-substituting and export-oriented products makes it possible to increase the share of small business in the export volume. The share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the total volume of exports in our republic was 10.2 percent in 2000, and increased to 28.9 percent in 2018 ^[10].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It can be noted that for the further development of entrepreneurship in our country, we consider it appropriate to implement the following measures:

- to widely promote the concept of entrepreneurship among the population of the country, to explain that as a result, they should engage in several types of activities in order to increase their income;
- paying special attention to ensuring economic growth in our country, creating new jobs, solving the employment problem, encouraging and supporting the increase of income and well-being of the population;
- based on the role and importance of the business sector in the economy, to ensure a suitable competitive environment for it in the economy;
- formation of the flow of investments aimed at the commercialization of innovations in business activities;
- creation of conditions (tax regime, customs policy, including measures aimed at creating a favorable investment environment) that ensure maximum responsiveness of business entities to innovations;
- helps to organize the production and sale of innovative business products on the market, thereby helping to develop innovative activities in small businesses.

List of references used:

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis of December 21, 2022.
2. Resolution PQ-3697 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of May 5, 2018 “On additional measures to create conditions for the development of active entrepreneurship and innovative activity”.
3. Decision PQ-212 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 19, 2022 “On measures to further expand the financing mechanisms of entrepreneurial projects in the regions”.
4. Margherita Ebraico (2015). An Assessment of the Performance of the Italian Tax Debt Collection System. Italia.Taxation papers
5. Sherov, A. (2018). Legal basis and importance of state financing of education system. International Finance and Accounting , 2018 (2), 92.
6. Muhammadjanovich K. I. Effective Directions of Development of Entrepreneurship //Conference Zone. - 2022. - S. 129-133.
7. Sharipov KB Improvement of the processes of specialization in small business activity. Dissertation abstract submitted for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics. -T.: “Academy publishing center” publishing house, 2020. 61 p
8. Aripov OAK Development of small business and private entrepreneurship and creation of a business environment. Scientific electronic magazine “Economy and innovative technologies”. No. 2, March-April, 2019
9. Kazakov, OS, & K amoliddinov I. (2021). Questions Of The Effective Utilization Of Industrial Resources In Enterprise Activity In The Conditions Of Economy Globalization. The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research , 3 (04), 114-119. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajjir/Volume03Issue04-18>
10. Data from the Statistics Department of Namangan Region.
11. www.agro.uz site information.

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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